

PERFORMANCE FEATURES OF CHANG INSTRUMENT AND CHANGSIMAN INSTRUMENTS

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Abstract: This article studies the performance characteristics of the zither and similar zither instruments. The historical development of these instruments, their place in various folk cultures, and their influence on musical performance styles are analyzed. The technical capabilities, sound range, resonance mechanism, and performance techniques of zither and zither instruments are scientifically covered. The article also analyzes the relevance and prospects of using these instruments in modern music education.

Keywords: zither, zither instruments, performance characteristics, musical culture, instrument technique, musical performance, modern music education.

Introduction

Chang instruments have a long history and occupy an important place in the musical heritage of the peoples of the world. The emergence and development of these instruments depends on the unique culture, customs and musical traditions of each nation. While the chang instrument is deeply rooted in the musical culture of the East, its modern interpretations are enriched with unique performance techniques in the performing arts of different nations.

The chang instrument is distinguished by its unique sound range, resonance mechanism and technical capabilities. It is successfully used not only in national music, but also in modern musical genres. Today, teaching chang and chang-like instruments in the music education system is gaining urgent importance not only as a means of training musicians, but also as a means of promoting national culture.

This article will study in detail the history, technical and performance characteristics of chang and chang-like instruments, as well as their role in modern musical performance. At the same time, the article will also analyze the scientific and methodological foundations of teaching these instruments.

Chang and percussion instruments play an important role in the musical culture of various peoples. These instruments have an ancient history and are widely used in the cultures of the peoples of the East, Central Asia, India, China and Europe. The basic structure of the Chang is often based on a stringed

resonance box, and sound is produced by striking the strings of the instrument. This feature gives the instrument a unique, resonant and clear sound.

The first appearances of the Chang date back to the times before Christ. In Chinese culture, the Chang-shaped instrument called "yangqin" is mentioned in ancient sources. In the musical culture of the peoples of Central Asia, the Chang was widely used mainly in performing folk songs, epics and instrumental works. In Uzbek and Tajik musical cultures, the Chang is recognized as an important instrument in maqom music.

The khan instrument consists of a sound box, strings and percussion sticks, the density and tension of the strings determine the specific sound of the instrument. The sound range depends on the size of the instrument and the number of strings. Typically, the khan instrument covers a wide range in the upper and lower octaves. This instrument plays an important role in harmonizing with other instruments.

The performance technique depends on the skill of the musician and the complexity of the musical work. The sticks (percussion sticks) used to strike the strings ensure the clarity and expressiveness of the instrument's sound. During the performance, each string vibrates to a certain extent, which ensures the depth and clarity of the sound. When playing the khan instrument, the technical skill, speed and musical taste of the performer are important.

Percussion instruments similar to the khan instrument are characteristic of different cultures, and their performance technique and structure differ slightly. For example, in Europe, the instrument called "cymbal" is one of the percussive instruments, which is also played by percussion, but its sound and style of performance are adapted to European music.

Today, the percussive instrument plays an important role in music education. Teaching the percussive instrument, improving its performance technique and combining it with modern technologies is one of the urgent issues in the development of national musical art and performing skills. The khangu is used as an effective tool in developing students' performance techniques, forming musical taste and rhythmic feelings. These materials scientifically demonstrate the unique place of the khangu in the performing arts and music education.

Discussion

Studying the performance characteristics of the khangu and khangu-like instruments helps to better understand their place in national and international musical culture. The technical capabilities and performance styles of these

instruments are successfully used not only in traditional music, but also in modern genres. Also, the role of the khangu in music education is gaining relevance, and its integration with modern pedagogical technologies makes the educational process more effective.

The cultural role of the khangu

The khangu plays an important role in providing melodiousness, expressiveness and dynamism in folk musical works. In particular, in Uzbekistan, the chang instrument is known as one of the main instruments of maqom art. It not only enhances the charm of the instrument in maqom works, but also deepens the philosophical and emotional content of the music.

Discussions on performance technique and skill requirements

The art of playing the chang instrument requires great technical skill from the performer. It is important to maintain subtlety and accuracy in hitting the strings with percussion sticks, as well as the rhythm and dynamics of the music. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the pedagogical approach to teaching the chang instrument. The use of audio-visual technologies and virtual training programs for the development of performance techniques in modern education is considered a promising solution.

Interaction of chang-like instruments

Chang-like instruments differ in performance technique, shape, and sound range in different regions of the world. For example, while the sound and performance technique of European instruments are in harmony with European musical traditions, Eastern instruments, including the khan, are distinguished by their melodiousness and emotional expressiveness. This diversity leads to the mutual enrichment of musical cultures.

Current issues in music education

In today's music education, it is necessary to develop specific pedagogical methods for teaching the khan instrument. The lack of textbooks and manuals on the khan instrument in music schools and higher educational institutions requires the intensification of research in this area. It is also necessary to strengthen the creative approach and promote national instruments to develop students' performing abilities.

The khan instrument and khan-like instruments are an integral part of the musical heritage, which provide rich opportunities not only in traditional performance, but also in modern musical experiments. Their study and development are of great importance in enriching musical art.

Conclusion

The changu and changu-like instruments occupy a unique place in world musical culture. The history of these instruments, their performance techniques, and their role in modern musical processes demonstrate that they are an integral part of a rich musical heritage. The changu is deeply rooted in the musical culture of the East, and its importance is especially emphasized in the maqom art of Uzbekistan.

The article analyzes the technical capabilities of the khangu, its sound range, resonance mechanism and specific aspects of its performance styles. The melodiousness and expressiveness of this instrument allow it to be successfully used not only in traditional but also in modern musical genres. The role of the khangu in music education and the possibilities of its effective use were also studied in detail.

Modern pedagogical technologies and innovative approaches are necessary for teaching the khangu in the modern education system and developing it as a means of promoting national culture. Also, by combining national and international musical experiences, the performance capabilities of this instrument can be further enriched.

The study of the khangu and khangu-like instruments serves not only to preserve the national musical heritage, but also to develop new musical directions. Therefore, their widespread introduction into the educational and performance process is considered one of the urgent tasks.

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